

University Governance as an Input to Strengthen Partnership with Local Community Organizations - A Comparative Study between Public and Private Universities

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Abstract: *The research aims to designate the role of university governance in strengthening the partnership with community organizations in Gaza Strip from the perspective of the personnel in the public and private universities. The researchers have used the descriptive analytical approach. The research community has included the personnel at (The Islamic University, Al-Azhar University, the University of Palestine, and the University of Gaza). The study tool is a questionnaire applied on a sample of personnel who have been chosen randomly. In the light of the questionnaire, we have got (228) questionnaire from public universities with a recovery of (94.2%) and (52) questionnaire from private universities with a recovery of (91.2%). Research Results have showed a statistically significant relationship between governance in all its dimensions (the laws and regulations, the academic freedom, the accountability, the responsibilities of the board of directors, the rights of all stakeholders, the disclosure and transparency) and strengthening the partnership between the universities and the civil society organizations from the perspective of the personnel in the public and private universities.*

Keywords: University Governance; Partnership; Local Community Organizations; Public Universities; Private Universities; Palestinian University; Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

The financial crises and internal and external challenges have negatively affected a number of public and private institutions, public and private companies, including universities, which are in urgent need of a framework that guarantees radical solutions to address conflicts of interest and lack of credibility in managing their financial resources. Financing and the scarcity of financial resources, and regulating their functioning with clear rules and laws with transparency, fair disclosure, and organizational effectiveness to achieve financial and administrative independence under the rules of good governance.

University education is the cornerstone for building the individual scientifically, culturally, socially and cognitively, and contributes to the development of society through the extension of all disciplines required by the labor market. The most recent concern among most countries is the development of university education through the application of university governance standards. The most important considerations are that governance is the framework that regulates and sets the objectives of higher education institutions and manages their resources and components according to the rules of transparency, participation and accountability in order to improve the quality of education according to the interests of students and society (Zoubi, 2012). The partnership is an important component of the economy in many countries. Inter-organizational projects contribute to the economic development of society and to employment opportunities in the public and private sectors.

The growth of joint ventures reflects the human value of work, support and care as an essential element in achieving development in all sectors. In addition provide equal employment opportunities for every person who is capable of considering the work as a right and a duty necessitated by the need to contribute to the building and development of society. The partnership is also a gateway to the preparation of a strategy for universities to enable them to identify the problems they face by identifying and choosing the appropriate strategic alternative, and thus to develop a sound perception of their practices and achieve the objectives and maximize the possibilities and resources for universities to achieve their goals of development, growth and continuity.

Governance is an essential platform for increasing the level of partnership between universities and civil society organizations so that through governance, it is possible to benefit from the strengths of some universities in the development of university education and to reduce the weaknesses of some universities. Partnership contributes to achieving the objectives better and increasing their viability, adaptation and growth. In this context, this paper examines the role of governance in achieving partnership between universities.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The system of higher education in Palestine in general and Gaza Strip in particular since 1967, and to date, it lacks many of the ingredients that make it transcends itself towards the horizon, as the policy of occupation of education produced serious shortcomings in the structure of Palestinian

education in the educational process is represented by inputs and outputs, content, frameworks and the extent to which it meets the needs of the society, where the higher education suffers from several crises, most notably the financial crisis resulting from political reasons, and the increasing number of colleges and universities in the absence of educational philosophy of the educational system, in addition to the lack of interest in scientific research, where several studies have pointed out that ignoring the institutions of higher education for the role that the private sector can play and ignoring the reliance on research results is one of the most important causes of the crisis experienced by institutions of higher education, in addition to the weak legislation governing partnerships and priorities of scientific research, fields, methods of follow-up and evaluation. In this sense, the main problem is how to develop and strengthen the partnership and benefit from it in the development of academic performance of universities in light of the reliance on the standards of university governance. Based on the above, the problem of the research is determined by the following question: What is the role of university governance in strengthening partnership with community organizations in Gaza Strip? A number of sub-questions arise from this question:

- What is the availability of the principles of governance (laws and regulations, transparency and disclosure, accounting and accountability, the rights of all beneficiaries, the responsibilities of the board of directors, and academic freedom) in Palestinian universities?
- To what extent do universities support partnership (partnership vision, message and objectives, partnership organization and management, partnership implementation) with community organizations?
- How well do governance principles contribute to strengthening partnership with community organizations?
- Do respondents differ on the extent to which governance contributes to strengthening the partnership in Palestinian universities according to the difference (qualification, years of service, type of university)?
- What are the constraints to implementing the partnership with community organizations?

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The aim of the research is to demonstrate the role of university governance in enhancing partnership with local community organizations operating in the Gaza Strip by achieving the following sub-objectives:

- Identify the availability of governance dimensions from the point of view of employees in public and private universities.

- Disclosure of the level of interest in the partnership from the point of view of employees in public and private universities.
- Determining the nature of the relationship between governance and achieving partnership from the point of view of workers in public and private universities in the Gaza Strip.
- To find out how different the opinions of the respondents on the relationship between governance and strengthening the partnership in Palestinian universities vary (qualification, years of service, type of university).
- Identify obstacles to the implementation of partnership with community organizations.

4. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The research derives its importance from its scientific subject as well as the field of its practical application. Therefore, the importance of research can be determined by the following aspects:

- The scientific enrichment it adds in the field of governance and partnership, which contributes to the clarification of the concepts of governance and partnership.
- Assisting universities in adapting and reacting to rapid environmental changes and changes and intense competition through their knowledge of their level of ownership of governance principles and partnership requirements.
- To contribute to the achievement of additional benefits for students and researchers, increase their satisfaction and achieve continuous and continuous development in providing services that meet their needs through partnership with community organizations.
- To draw the attention of decision makers in universities to the need to know the role of governance in strengthening partnership with community organizations, in the light of the results of the study and to benefit from them in the field of application.

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

In order to provide an appropriate answer to the research questions presented, the research seeks to test the validity of the following hypotheses:

H01: There is no statistically significant relationship between university governance and strengthening partnership with local community organizations from the point of view of workers in public and private universities in the Gaza Strip.

H02: There are no statistically significant differences between respondents' views on the relationship between university governance and the promotion of partnership with local community organizations according to the different

types of qualifications (years of service, type of university) from the point of view of workers in public and private universities in the Gaza Strip.

6. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

- **Subject Limit (Academic):** The study was limited in its objective to study University Governance as an Input to Strengthen Partnership with Local Community Organizations - A Comparative Study between Public and Private Universities
- **Human Limit:** The study was conducted on workers in private Palestinian universities operating in Gaza Strip except for services in the universities in question.
- **Institutional limit:** The study was conducted in the State of Palestine, and was limited to 4 universities: (Islamic University, Al-Azhar University, Palestine University and Gaza University).
- **The spatial limit:** The study was conducted in the State of Palestine - Gaza Strip.

7. LITERATURE REVIEW

Study of (Alshaer et al., 2017) aimed to demonstrate the role of public universities in promoting partnership with non-governmental organizations in Gaza Strip from the point of view of employees in public universities. The researcher used the descriptive analytical method. The research community consisted of the employees of the Islamic University and Al-Azhar University. The study tool was a questionnaire applied to a simple random sample of employees. A questionnaire was obtained by 228 responses with a recovery rate of 94.2%. The study concluded that there is a statistically significant relationship between governance in all its dimensions (laws and regulations, academic freedom, accounting and accountability, the responsibilities of the board of directors, the rights of all the beneficiaries, transparency and disclosure) and strengthening the partnership between universities and civil society organizations. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is the need to work on applying the principles of governance, especially after the world has recently witnessed environmental, social and economic phenomena that have clearly affected the financial and administrative performance of many international institutions. The need to focus on human resources and their knowledge of the rules and principles of governance in addition to providing them with all the latest developments and scientific information in this area, and that the departments of universities focused on training programs, seminars and seminars specialized in governance, and the integration of some specialized scientific materials of governance in the courses taught by the scientific.

Study of (AL- hila et al., 2017) aimed to demonstrate the impact of private universities' governance in building partnership with NGOs operating in Gaza Strip. The

researchers used the descriptive analytical method, and the research population consists of employees in the universities in Gaza Strip. It was applied on the University of Palestine and the University of Gaza. A random sample of (57) employees was selected and (52) responses were obtained with a rate of (91.2%). The results of the study showed that the level of availability of the principles of governance in the universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of workers was high. The relative weight of private universities was 67%. The order of principles is as follows: (laws and regulations, academic freedom, accounting and accountability, board responsibilities, the rights of all stakeholders, transparency and disclosure). The results showed that the level of partnership in private universities from the point of view of workers was high. The relative weight of private universities was 74.5%. The results of the study also showed that there is a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between governance in all its dimensions and strengthening the partnership between universities and NGOs. The study concluded with a set of recommendations, the most important of which is the necessity to work on the interest and benefit from the principles of governance available in the private universities in the Gaza Strip through the preparation of a document for the university governance which includes the identification of the tasks, processes and responsibilities assigned to each member, and the need to increase the level of partnership between private universities on the one hand and community organizations on the other hand, as well as the need to follow up the Ministry of Education to the extent to which universities in Palestine adhere to the principles and rules of governance. Oblige all institutions to disclose and transparency standards and to present the outcomes of their work to the beneficiaries of these services. The establishment of a special unit for partnership and community development, which will support the positive relationship between the university and community institutions. Work to remove all obstacles that limit the partnership between universities and community organizations, the most important of which is the limited powers granted to universities and the weak funding allocated to partnerships where the Ministry of Education and Higher Education can support projects based on partnership, as well as the need to link between production centers and the needs of the community through the development of a clear plan, the philosophy, goals and criteria of partnership with the participation of all parties.

Study of (Mahrous, 2016) which aims to identify the theoretical foundations of corporate governance in contemporary universities, as well as to identify the reality of corporate governance and to know the different ways to activate corporate governance. The study found that the organization's performance of its work using the means and methods by which the institution determines its direction according to a set of foundations leads to the activation of corporate governance, and that there is a set of theoretical

foundations for institutional governance in contemporary universities, namely the distribution of authority and tasks among administrative units, between the administrative entity and the surrounding environment. The study also revealed that the reality of participatory academic governance and the governance of stakeholders in the Faculty of Education, Ain Shams University, among faculty members and administrators is medium.

Study of (Abdo, 2015) which aims to analyze the relationship between the strategy of partnership and the quality of educational services and achieve the development of competitive excellence in public and private universities, and to reveal the nature of the leadership of the university leadership towards the implementation of the partnership strategy, as well as to identify the constraints and obstacles facing the implementation of the partnership strategy. The study concluded that the partnership is a framework that enables universities, if they activate their components, to improve the quality of services and achieve competitive excellence.

Study of (Khater, 2015) which aimed at analyzing the intellectual framework related to the nature of the partnership between the universities and productive institutions and their fields, and the bases on which they are based, in addition to presenting proposed formulas for the strategic partnership between universities and productive institutions in Egypt. The lack of awareness of the partnership culture, its areas and levels between the university institutions and the production institutions, and the weak organization and implementation of the university for partnership and management, where it obtained a middle degree, weak activation of partnership with community institutions,

Study of (Al-Arini, 2014), which aims to identify the reality of applying governance from the point of view of faculty members and employees of the Imam Mohammed bin Saud Islamic University in Saudi Arabia. The study found that there were statistically significant differences between the responses of the sample of the study and the reality of applying the governance in Imam University due to the difference (scientific qualification, the nature of the current job, and the years of experience).

Study of (Harkavy et al., 2014) which aims to provide an overview of institutional efforts to support Pennsylvania State University and its role as a central institution through effective governance, as well as to recognize the role of the University in building sustainable partnerships with other universities. The study found that there is an effort at the Pennsylvania State University to strengthen its role as a partner institution in civil society. The study noted that effective governance plays a major role in increasing the progress of work among faculty members. The study also shows that governance contributes to the participation of students through community service As well as working to develop many sustainable partnerships in the community.

Study of (Okwelle and Wordu, 2014) which aims to explore the impact of public-private partnership on the quality of the educational process in Nigerian universities. The study aimed to identify the role of public-private partnership in education through a strategy to improve the quality of the technical education program in Nigeria. The study found that there is a strong relationship between the partnership and the quality of educational services in sixteen universities in southwestern Nigeria. The study showed that the success of the partnership depends on the ability of the government sector to identify private sector partners and that there is a complementary role between the public and private sectors, and Effective VET system.

Study of (Abdul Fattah, 2013) aimed at identifying the role of strategic direction in supporting the sustainable competitiveness of commercial banks through the application of the standards of governance and identifying the compatibility of banking practices in Egyptian commercial banks with the standards of governance. The study found that there is a role for the strategic direction in applying the standards of governance and that this environment allows care and attention to the human element in order to encourage creativity and innovation which leads to supporting the competitive competitiveness of commercial banks. The study showed that the commitment of employees to apply the standards of governance as a strategic direction for banking policies helps in support of the sustainable competitiveness of Egyptian commercial banks based on competitive and renewable competitive advantages based on the personal and behavioral characteristics of creative and innovative employees.

Study of (Hristova and Klisarovska, 2013) which aims to provide an overview of the PPP projects in Europe and assess them in the current situation, as well as identify key projects that need public-private partnership. The study found that public-private partnerships in many European countries are a key tool for implementing infrastructure projects. The study shows that public-private partnerships lead to the distribution of risks to public and private sector partners as well as improving the quality of public and private services, Study that public-private partnerships lead to a change in the role of the public sector from direct participation to regulation and control.

Study of (AL-Hariri, 2010) aimed at determining the nature and forms of the relationship between business organizations or the private sector and government universities in the Republic of Yemen, as well as identifying ways to strengthen and develop the relationship between the Yemeni universities. The study found that the most important elements for successful partnership between the private sector and universities is the availability of funding. The results of the study indicate that there are mechanisms that lead to positive results in the success of the partnership between the private sector and the universities.

Study of (Abdul Hakim, 2010), which aims to develop a proposed strategy for developing open education

management in Egyptian universities in light of the principles of governance, as well as to know if the Egyptian experience in open education depended on embracing the traditional universities of open education centers according to the principles of governance. The study found that the development of management practices and adherence to the principles of governance are working to develop open education in universities.

Study of (Tetevová, 2010) which aims at identifying the obstacles of partnership between the university and the private and public sectors in the Czech Republic, as well as clarifying the importance of the social responsibility of the three sides of the university, the private sector and the public sector, and the impact of tripartite cooperation between the university and the public sector on the quality of the educational process and scientific research. The study found that the university plays a major role in supporting economic and social development in society through the transfer of knowledge. The study also showed that the public sector and the private sector have a role in increasing the level of university funding, which leads to the success of the partnership between the university and the public and private sectors. An important role for the partnership between the university and the public and private sectors, which contribute to enhance the reputation of the university and improve its image and excellence from other educational institutions competition and improve its ability to provide quality educational services and increase the efficiency and satisfaction and loyalty of workers in Here.

7.1 Comment on previous studies

There is a great importance and a role for cooperation between universities and the private sector where they can be used to establish and promote an effective partnership between universities and the community.

In terms of the objective of the study: The research trends of previous studies aimed at identifying the theoretical foundations of institutional governance in contemporary universities, as well as the reality of governance. In addition, most studies focused on knowing the role of partnership between universities and the private sector only without focusing on their role with labor organizations. The study will deal with the dimensions of governance, especially from the administrative side and specifically the universities, and the view of the workers on the governance of universities as an input to the Aziz partnership with local community organizations through comparison between public and private universities.

In terms of the variables of the study: Most studies focused on the accounting variables, especially transparency and disclosure, dealt with the dimensions of governance in a different way, where the dimensions (application of laws and regulations, transparency and disclosure, accounting and accountability, attention to the rights of all the beneficiaries, determination of the responsibilities of the board, academic freedom). The current study differed from previous Arab and foreign studies in terms of field of application, methods of

analysis, period of time, and nature of the sample that were dealt with.

8. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

8.1 Governance:

The expansion of the size of the projects led to the separation of ownership from the administration. These projects began to seek stronger sources of management. The expansion of the size of companies and the separation of ownership from the administration led to weak mechanisms for supervising the actions of managers and many companies in financial crises. In the late 1990s, crises followed. Perhaps the most important of these was the crisis of Enron WorldCom in the United States in 2001, which prompted the world to take care of governance. The need for governance emerged in many advanced and emerging economies over the past few decades, Economic and financial crises.

8.2 The concept of governance:

The term governance has emerged in the past few decades and it is expected that this term will have a wide range of use and deliberation in many countries, developing or advanced, or in the path of economic transformation.

Like globalization, it has begun to take on multiple dimensions such as political governance (good governance), environmental governance, social governance, corporate governance and institutions, and banking governance. In most studies, governance has been associated with the concept of transparency to form two sides of a single coin.

The definitions of governance varied in terms of the number of people interested in the term and their political, cultural, economic and social affiliations, and the multiplicity of interests and their overlapping of the same term, and the definitions we provide will be, for example, not limited to and close to the concept of corporate governance, which is the closest to the economic and banking dimension in our brief presentation on corporate governance.

Governance is a set of laws, regulations and decisions that aim to achieve quality and excellence in performance by selecting appropriate and effective methods to achieve corporate plans and objectives.

In other words, governance means the system, that is, the existence of systems that govern relationships between key players that affect performance, and the long-term strengthening of the institution and the identification of responsibility and responsibility (Najjar, 2006).

Corporate governance also refers to the following characteristics (Hammad, 2005):

- Discipline: any proper and correct ethical conduct.
- Transparency: providing a true picture of everything that happens.
- Independence - that is, there are no unnecessary effects and pressures to work.
- Accountability: the ability to evaluate and assess the work of the Board of Directors and the Executive Management.

- Responsibility: Any responsibility for all stakeholders in the organization.
- Justice: the rights of different stakeholder groups in the institution must be respected.
- Social responsibility: Any consideration of the institution as a new citizen.

A. Definition of Governance:

The concept of governance has attracted the attention of many academics, researchers, analysts and practitioners. The definitions of governance have increased and their concept has grown over time. In this context, it has been difficult to come up with a unified definition of this term. Governance is the translation of the term "governance." And some governance definitions can be presented as follows:

- 1- The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) defines it as the rules and procedures that ensure that the organization is properly and effectively managed, including that managers and employees act appropriately and in accordance with sound laws and practices (Glossary, 2004).
- 2- UNDP defines it as the system of policies and values in which enterprises manage their various affairs and through interactions with the environment (UNDP, 2004).
- 3- The World Bank considers that the behaviors that reflect the exercise of authority and self-control of universities reflect the structure, structure and function of the institutions of university education as a whole, the regulatory and legislative framework for monitoring them, the roles and responsibilities of the university administration and its relation to the society and its attempt to achieve quality and excellence in university performance.).
- 4- Hammad (2005) defines it as the system through which the Organization's work is directed and monitored at the highest level in order to achieve its objectives and to meet the standards of responsibility, integrity and openness.
- 5- Wang (2008) sees it as a set of laws, regulations and instructions aimed at achieving quality and excellence by selecting appropriate and effective strategies to achieve the University's goals and objectives.
- 6- As defined by Ali (2007), it is a set of mechanisms, procedures, laws, systems and decisions that ensure: discipline, transparency and fairness and thus aim at achieving quality and excellence in performance by activating the management's actions with regard to exploiting the economic resources available to it, Stakeholders and society as a whole.

The researchers define governance in universities as a set of principles that include: laws and regulations, transparency and disclosure, accounting and accountability, attention to the rights of all the beneficiaries, the responsibilities of the

board of directors, and academic freedom in universities that contribute to the achievement of strategic objectives.

B. Governance Objectives:

Good corporate governance aims to achieve a wide range of goals (Greet, 2004):

- 1- Maximize corporate performance.
- 2- To establish regulations to avoid or minimize fraud, conflict of interest, and all unacceptable behaviors, materially, administratively and morally.
- 3- Setting up control systems for the management of the company and its board of directors.
- 4- Establish systems under which the company is managed according to structures that define and distribute both rights and responsibilities (board of directors and shareholders).
- 5- The establishment of necessary and necessary rules and procedures related to the functioning of the company, including the achievement of the objectives of corporate governance.
- 6- Good governance can achieve financial and administrative reform and reduce corruption, as well as increase the confidence of stakeholders as current or potential investors in the output of the accounting system and reports issued by corporate departments according to international accounting and auditing standards complemented by the principles of corporate governance.

C. Advantages of applying governance in universities:

Hamdouna (2016) believes that one of the most important advantages of implementing governance in universities is the following:

1. Establish an accounting system for all parties associated with universities.
2. Prevent universities from being exposed to potential crises.
3. Improve university performance, improve economic efficiency and increase economic growth by providing appropriate conditions.
4. To create incentives and incentives for the university board of directors to pursue the achievement of the goals that achieve the interest of the university through effective supervision of the universities.
5. To provide a competitive position for the university in comparison to other universities and to increase its ability to attract academics who can support financial growth.
6. Strengthening integrity and efficiency in universities.
7. Give more attention to environmental and ethical issues in the educational system.
8. Improving the rates of academic scholars and the stability of university staff.

D. Principles and Foundations of Governance:

The concept of governance is fundamentally related to the behavior of the various categories involved. Therefore, there is a set of principles that must be met in these behaviors in order to achieve the purpose of applying governance in universities. These principles constitute the basic pillars of governance. The most important are the following (Sami, 2009):

1. **Transparency and disclosure:** Providing a clear and true picture of everything that happens, in order to ensure the achievement of confidence, integrity and objectivity in the management procedures. It also ensures proper and timely disclosure of the important issues. This feature provides financial and non-financial accounting and disclosure information, and the information is correct, clear and complete. Transparency ensures timely and accurate disclosure of all matters related to the provision of information on financial and operating results, objectives and board members, salaries and benefits to senior officials, and structures and policies.
2. **Compliance with laws and regulations** The preparation and review of the application of laws and regulations in a manner consistent with quality standards and also in accordance with the requirements of regulatory processes should be prepared and reviewed in order to provide objective scrutiny of the method used in the preparation of financial statements and the preparation of financial reports.
3. **Accountability and responsibility:** It is intended to provide a clear organizational structure that sets the points of authority and responsibility, and to hold officials and decision makers accountable for their responsibility towards the company and shareholders. Accountability is a rule for accounting for decision makers or those who carry out business, the results of their decisions and actions towards shareholders and other stakeholders. Find a mechanism to achieve this principle.
4. **Clarity:** It is intended that the financial statements and reports should be clear, transparent and fair in their preparation. To do so, management and the Audit Committee should investigate the general understanding of the financial statements.
5. **Independence:** The mechanism that reduces or eliminates conflicts of interest. This mechanism starts from the formation of boards and appointing committees to appoint an independent, efficient and qualified external auditor who performs his work according to the requirements of professional care and assets to confirm or certify that the financial statements represent the truth of the financial position and performance.
1. **Equity:** The framework of governance practices should protect shareholders as they have certain property rights, namely, the right to secure property registration methods, the right to elect directors, the right to receive a share of profits, the right to vote in the general

assembly of shareholders, The right to transfer or transfer ownership of shares, the right to receive the various necessary information relevant to the activity in a timely and systematic manner (Abdul Malik, 2008).

2. **Equitable treatment of shareholders:** Governance ensures equal treatment of all shareholders, including minority and foreign shareholders, where everyone must have the same rights, and everyone should have access to information.
3. **Role of stakeholders:** The governance framework should involve recognition of the rights of stakeholders that have been established in accordance with the law, and should also encourage cooperation between them and the company and enable them to access the information required.
4. **Responsibilities of the Board of Directors:** The corporate governance practice should provide strategic guidelines for guidance. It should ensure follow-up to the Executive Management by the Board of Directors and ensure that the Board of Directors is accountable to shareholders.

E. Constraints on Governance:

There are a number of constraints to the application of governance in organizations in general, and in universities in particular can be summarized as follows (Khurshid and Yusuf, 2009):

1. Culture in society.
2. The general political climate inside and outside the university.
3. University legislation and legislation of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research.
4. University Management Method.
5. The mechanism of selection of members of the teaching and administrative bodies.
6. Absence of faculty members from university life.
7. Non-involvement of employees in public activities within the university.

8.3 Partnership:

The theme of partnership between different sectors is of great interest to governments, communities and research centers around the world, after it has become clear that the process of economic and social development depends on mobilizing and gathering the full potential of the community, including resources, resources and expertise. Institutional organizations that establish and operate projects of various types after the separate and independent sectorial institutional organizations have encountered challenges and difficulties in achieving the development goals at the ambitious target levels. Therefore, both developed and developing countries seek to create Institutions, legislation and systems to adopt participatory organizations in which all sectors of society contribute to the direction, management, operation, development and development of projects and businesses in order to serve their purposes on the basis of cooperative participation, good governance, transparent accountability and mutual benefit.

Not only is it necessary to ensure the success of the partnership in terms of legislation and regulations, but also to create links between them and the concept of governance. Both have multiple dimensions with administrative, legal, economic and social aspects. They meet in common points based on the principles of transparency and disclosure, accountability and equal rights of stakeholders. Responsibilities to improve resource utilization, enhance competitiveness, attract sources of funding, expand projects to create new jobs, support economic stability, and partnership in universities and other sectors are still in the process of developing common principles, rules and regulations which governs and regulates the various forms of partnerships between the public and private sectors covering all economic and social sectors.

A. Partnership concept:

The concept of partnership is a relatively recent concept in the field of universities. The word partnership has been used by many researchers without giving a precise definition. In this context, the partnership can be defined as:

1. Collaboration between two or more organizations aimed at reducing time and increasing information, knowledge, skills and financial resources (Reed, 2009).
2. A cooperative agreement between two or more organizations to work together for a common purpose, taking into account the sharing of risks, responsibilities, resources, competencies and benefits to all partners (Richter, 2004).
3. Partnership with universities is a series of personal relationships between community members, employees, students and faculty to achieve an advertised and beneficial goal for all parties (Gerhardt, 2009).
4. All forms of inter-institutional cooperation for a certain period aimed at strengthening the effectiveness of dealers in order to achieve the goals identified (Dealtry, 2008).
5. Interactions and cooperation between economic and social institutions to achieve a better competitive situation (Al-Rashid, 2006).

The researchers know the partnership as the establishment of universities in cooperation and the establishment of varying relations with the civil institutions so that each maintain its independence in terms of goals and interests to achieve a set of common goals.

B. Partnership Forms:

The partnership has many forms, depending on the relationship between the partners. The partnership is based on the objectives of each partner. The most important forms of partnership can be presented as follows (Mustafa, 2000):

1. **Industrial partnership:** Because of the development and complexity of the process of manufacturing through the difficulty of keeping pace with modern production methods as well as technological development emerged this type of partnership, which often takes the form of work plans, and highlights the need to establish what is known as technical cooperation from the large costs

allocated to industrial projects on the one hand, It requires high technology, and the method of industrial partnership achieves the transfer of technology and modern administrative knowledge more effectively. In this context, some organizations resort to convergence and establish teams or groups specializing in advanced technological and industrial projects for several reasons. The motives for this type of partnership in various areas are:

- The economic sphere in order to benefit from the impact of scale, research and development costs.
 - The technical field where the advantages of advanced technology and creativity are tapped.
 - In order to benefit from consumer preferences and strengthen distribution networks.
2. **Business partnership:** This formula is the joint cooperation between two or more institutions that suffer from the weakness of their business and therefore resort to partnership which may be in the form of concession contracts, licensing agreements, supply agreements, which allows to reduce the costs of business transactions and the opening of new distribution networks which affects the business positively.
 3. **Technical Partnership:** This form of partnership emerged as a result of changes in the technological field and increased costs of research and innovation. This type of partnership can be divided into:
 - R and D agreements: Many governments and companies allocate funds to spend on basic and applied research. This formula is used to benefit from second-party experience as well as funding and risk reduction. Among the sectors in which this type of partnership - Research, research and development centers between universities - the field of advanced industry - electronic services and products - the field of information - information technology).
 - Knowledge transfer agreements: This formula allows the partner to benefit from the transfer of knowledge of economic value that is important to help achieve maximum efficiency and profitability as well as raise its competitive level at the level of the general environment.
 - License Agreement: Under this Agreement, the Partner grants a License to the Second Party to access certain technologies or to take advantage of the technological aspect for a long but specific period. This Agreement is of a bilateral nature.
 4. **Financial Partnership:** This type of partnership is related to the degree of the partner's participation in the second partner's capital through direct investment. This formula gives the right to guide the management and policies of the partner whose capital has been contributed to the interests of the partner invested in the development of his products and marketing efforts.

C. Principles of Partnership:

Sustainable and effective partnership depends on a set of principles (Medhat, 2011):

1. Honesty, trust, mutual respect, equality, transparency and accountability.
2. Work as a unit to achieve common goals.
3. Respect differences among partners and make appropriate decision based on consensus and resource utilization.
4. Accounting, compliance, clarity, financial policy development and sound accounting systems.
5. Agreement on rules of engagement and relations between members of the same team.
6. Cooperation and integration, continuity of communication and sharing of rights and duties.
7. Awareness of the environment and the community and encourage partnerships.

In addition, researchers can identify the most important foundations and principles of partnership in the field of universities and civil society organizations in particular:

1. The partnership with universities is based on clear and specific principles, principles, rights and duties.
2. That the partnership is part of a strategic plan with specific objectives and a common mechanism for implementation.
3. Changing the concept of partnership with universities from the concept of social support to the concept of development support.
4. The partnership is based on the principle of achieving mutual interests between universities and civil society organizations.
5. The partnership is concerned with maintaining social goals, objectives, requirements and policies.

8.4 Application of governance in universities to achieve partnership with civil society:

A. The stages of applying governance in universities to partnership with civil society

Based on previous studies, five stages can be identified for the application of governance in universities:

Phase One: Definition of Governance and Formation of a Supporting Opinion:

It is the most important and most dangerous stage at this stage. It is at this stage to clarify the features and aspects of governance, to define its dimensions and concepts, to clarify its methods, tools and messages, as well as to distinguish between governance as culture, behavior and commitment, and governance as a basis for fair transactions.

Phase 2: Building Governance Infrastructure:

Governance is a strong infrastructure, an ability to absorb its movement and an ability to interact with its variants. It is a complex and extended structure. Infrastructure is absolutely necessary to establish governance, achieve understanding and effective coexistence among different parties, and infrastructure is an important and binding element for establishing governance. It is divided into two parts: an

overarching infrastructure for governance and the institutional organizational entity (governing boards), which are the supervisors of its implementation at the university level, as well as an infrastructure of governance, which includes the basic and ethical basis for the application of governance.

Phase 3: Develop a standard program of governance and identify indicators:

The application of governance requires a time-bound schedule of work, tasks and duties. Through obedience, compliance and compliance systems, all expected and desired goals are met.

Phase 4: Implementing and Implementing Governance:

The stage at which real tests begin and the degree of willingness of all parties to apply governance. Governance, as well as freedoms, also has governing constraints and prudential controls.

Phase 5: Monitoring and Development of Governance:

Monitoring and follow-up is the main tool used by the University for good Governance Implementation. It is a control of an integral and complementary nature, which has two main functions: a remedial function to address any error or failure occurring, and an innovative preventive function based on Tools and means that increase the effectiveness of governance. Thus, the development of an organizational, administrative or supervisory unit of governance within the administrative structure and organizational structure of the university will help to perform the function of oversight in governance, as it needs an internal control body to monitor the implementation of the values of governance and to maintain the ethics and values.

B. Advantages of Partnership between Palestinian Universities and Community Organizations:

The benefits of this partnership can be summarized as follows:

- **Technology transfer:** Technology is an important factor for the development of community organizations, which often rely on technology to deliver their services. However, it costs the organization high amounts. The partnership method is therefore an appropriate way to transfer technology to local organizations in an easy and cost-effective manner.
- **Improve the potential:** By improving the status of CBOs through the transfer of knowledge that allows for improved joint performance as this relationship has a direct and significant impact on increasing its capabilities and allows to reduce problems and bring new potentials and possibilities by creating additional opportunities to participate in new sectors and areas and complementary to the main activity of it.
- **Entering new areas:** This is achieved by selecting the right partner that minimizes the impact of constraints and determinants that impede entry into new and multiple areas by exploiting information about opportunities that help develop their capacity to reach appropriate capacity.

- **Education and training and acquisition of new skills:**
The friction between the partners for a long time is somewhat allows to learn and acquire some new skills, through changes in the curricula and technical methods to learn and transfer these skills because of the reliance on new and advanced programs for the preparation and training of workers.

9. FIELD STUDY

9.1 Methodology of the study

Based on the nature of the study and the objectives it seeks to achieve, the analytical descriptive method is used, which is based on the study of the phenomenon as it is in reality and is concerned as a precise description and expressed in qualitative and quantitative terms. This approach is not sufficient to collect information about the phenomenon in order to investigate its manifestations and its

different relations, But rather to analysis, linkage and interpretation.

9.2 Society and sample of the study

The research community consists of all (1341) employees in the universities in Gaza Strip. The research has been applied to the following universities (Islamic University, Palestine University, Al-Azhar University, Gaza University). A random sample of 247 of public University employees was selected, with a total of (57) of private University employees was selected, a total of (228) responses were obtained at a recovery rate of (94.2%) for public universities, and (52) responses of private universities at a recovery rate of (91.2%). The distribution of the sample of the study according to the personal data of the individuals in it as follows:

Table 1: Distribution of Study Sample Individuals

Personal data		Public Universities	Private Universities	Public Universities and Private Universities
Qualification	Ph.D.	62	12	74
	M.A.	61	14	75
	BA	83	19	102
	Diploma	22	7	29
Number of years of service	Less than 5 years	55	11	66
	From 5 - less than 10 years	65	21	86
	From 10 - under 15 years	71	8	79
	15 years and over	37	12	49
Total		٢٢٨	٥٢	٢٨٠

9.3 Validity of the search tool:

The tool of the research means that the tool measures what has been set for measurement, and has verified the validity of the questionnaire through the following methods:

1. Validity from the point of view of the arbitrators

The questionnaire was presented to a number of (5) specialized arbitrators in order to ensure the accuracy of the language of the questionnaire, the clarity of the instructions

of the questionnaire, the affiliation of the paragraphs to the dimensions of the questionnaire and the validity of this tool to measure the objectives associated with this research from the point of view of the arbitrators.

2. True internal consistency

The reliability of internal consistency was calculated by finding correlation coefficients for the identification axes, as shown in the following table:

Table 2: The internal consistency of the identification axes is confirmed

The Hub	Public Universities			Private Universities		
	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance
Governance fields	0.842	0.000	Sig at 0.01	0.962	0.000	Sig at 0.01
Partnership fields	0.894	Sig at 0.01	0.808	Sig at 0.01
Field of the obstacles of partnership	0.889	0.000	Sig at 0.01	0.641	0.000	Sig at 0.01

The above table shows that the axes of the questionnaire have statistically significant correlation coefficients. This indicates that the axes of the questionnaire have high reliability coefficients.

9.4 Stability of the study instrument:

The tool means that the tool yields the same results if applied again to the same group of individuals, ie, the results do not change. The questionnaire is confirmed by the following methods:

1. Stability using the formula Alpha Cronbach:

Table 3: Correlation coefficients using the Alpha Cronbach equation for the resolution axes

The Hub	Public Universities	Private Universities
	Coefficient of correlation	Coefficient of correlation
Governance fields	0.843	0.853
Partnership fields	0.847	0.755
Field of the obstacles of partnership	0.804	0.891
The resolution as a whole	0.923	0.908

The above table shows that correlation coefficients for the identification axes are high stability coefficients, and are met for research purposes.

2. Stability in half-split way:

Table 4: Split-Half way correlation coefficients for the point of resolution

The Hub	Coefficient of correlation			
	Public Universities		Private Universities	
	Before the amendment	After modification	Before the amendment	After modification
Governance fields	0.938	0.968	0.958	0.979
Partnership fields	0.836	0.956	0.856	0.922
Field of the obstacles of partnership	0.837	0.904	0.857	0.923
The resolution as a whole	0.762	0.865	0.895	0.945

The above table shows that the half-term correlation coefficients of the resolution axes are high stability coefficients and meet the study objectives.

The stability of the search tool was determined by calculating the coefficients of the correlation coefficients using the alpha-cronbach formula, as shown in the following table:

The stability of the search tool was determined by calculating the correlation coefficients in the split-half way of the identification axes, as shown in the following table:

The question is: What is the availability of the principles of governance (laws and regulations, transparency and disclosure, accounting and accountability, the rights of all stakeholders, the responsibilities of the board of directors, academic freedom) in Palestinian universities from the point of view of university staff?

This question was answered using the "T" test for one sample, as shown in the following table:

10. ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY FIELDS

10.1 Results of the first question:

Table 5: Analysis of the pillars of governance

No.	Item	Universities	SMA	Standard Deviation	"T" Values	"Sig." value	Relative weight	Ranking
Laws and regulations								
1.	The University seeks to develop laws and regulations in force.	Public	3.794	0.731	16.397	0.000	75.877	١
		Private	3.846	0.894	6.824	0.000	76.923	٢
2.	The applicable laws shall set appropriate penalties for the types of offenses against the beneficiaries.	Public	3.680	0.806	12.729	0.000	73.596	٣
		Private	3.635	0.886	5.164	0.000	72.692	٣
3.	Check the laws and regulations in place at the University Community Justice.	Public	3.360	0.679	8.004	0.000	67.193	٥
		Private	3.346	0.861	2.901	0.005	66.923	٥
4.	The laws and regulations in force encourage the effective participation of	Public	3.539	0.770	10.577	0.000	70.789	٤
		Private	3.500	1.076	3.352	0.002	70.000	٤

No.	Item	Universities	SMA	Standard Deviation	"T" Values	"Sig." value	Relative weight	Ranking
	all the beneficiaries in the university.							
5.	The University applies all regulations and instructions of the accreditation body of Palestinian higher education institutions.	Public	3.732	0.831	13.312	0.000	74.649	۲
		Private	3.942	0.873	7.788	0.000	78.846	۱
Fields as a whole		Public	3.621	0.508	18.467	0.000	72.421	
		Private	3.654	0.621	7.588	0.000	73.077	
Transparency and disclosure								
1.	The University shall take into account the clarity of the application of the regulations and the regulations for all its employees.	Public	3.513	0.950	8.154	0.000	70.263	۱
		Private	3.423	0.893	3.415	0.001	68.462	۱
2.	The University discloses its policies in granting bonuses and allowances to all its members.	Public	3.149	1.140	1.975	0.049	62.982	۳
		Private	2.942	1.259	-0.330	0.742	58.846	۳
3.	The University discloses the criteria for holding leadership and administrative positions.	Public	3.263	1.103	3.602	0.000	65.263	۲
		Private	3.192	1.030	1.347	0.184	63.846	۲
4.	The university is transparently informed of the factors related to the significant risks that threaten the university.	Public	3.096	0.980	1.487	0.138	61.930	۴
		Private	2.923	0.837	-0.663	0.510	58.462	۴
5.	The University discloses all performance reports.	Public	2.952	1.050	-0.694	0.489	59.035	۵
		Private	2.731	1.012	-1.918	0.061	54.615	۵
Fields as a whole		Public	3.195	0.877	3.355	0.001	63.895	
		Private	3.042	0.776	0.393	0.696	60.846	
Accounting and Accountability								
1.	The University provides clear rules and accountability for the performance of its academic and administrative members.	Public	3.311	1.064	4.420	0.000	66.228	۳
		Private	3.558	0.916	4.389	0.000	71.154	۲
2.	The work of the University is administratively and academically supervised by internal and external bodies.	Public	3.548	0.994	8.325	0.000	70.965	۱
		Private	3.577	1.036	4.017	0.000	71.538	۱
3.	The University takes corrective action based on accountability reports.	Public	3.307	1.059	4.378	0.000	66.140	۴
		Private	3.404	0.934	3.117	0.003	68.077	۴
4.	The University identifies key performance indicators for each employee.	Public	3.158	1.079	2.209	0.028	63.158	۵
		Private	3.269	0.843	2.303	0.025	65.385	۵
5.	University staff clearly understand the rules to be followed and the consequences of their violation.	Public	3.531	0.959	8.356	0.000	70.614	۲
		Private	3.500	1.146	3.146	0.003	70.000	۳
Fields as a whole		Public	3.371	0.818	6.852	0.000	67.421	
		Private	3.462	0.753	4.419	0.000	69.231	
The rights of all beneficiaries								
1.	The University employee demands his or her rights at any time in accordance with fair rules and regulations.	Public	3.368	1.047	5.311	0.000	67.368	۲
		Private	3.231	1.022	1.629	0.110	64.615	۲
2.	The functions of the beneficiaries shall be facilitated in accordance with the laws and regulations in force at the University.	Public	3.443	0.780	8.571	0.000	68.860	۱
		Private	3.346	1.027	2.431	0.019	66.923	۱
3.	The university follows the method of dialogue in reaching decisions through the concerned committees and the	Public	3.189	0.950	2.997	0.003	63.772	۴
		Private	2.981	0.960	-0.144	0.886	59.615	۵

No.	Item	Universities	SMA	Standard Deviation	"T" Values	"Sig." value	Relative weight	Ranking
	beneficiaries.							
4.	The University involves representatives from the local community, academics, administrators and students in developing development plans.	Public	3.136	1.051	1.953	0.052	62.719	๐
		Private	3.000	1.103	0.000	1.000	60.000	๔
5.	The University provides a system for receiving, complaining and dealing with university employees' proposals.	Public	3.219	1.022	3.240	0.001	64.386	๓
		Private	3.154	0.937	1.184	0.242	63.077	๓
Fields as a whole		Public	3.271	0.749	5.464	0.000	65.421	
		Private	3.142	0.723	1.419	0.162	62.846	
Responsibilities of the Board of Directors								
1.	Members of the Board of Directors shall be permanently resident.	Public	3.096	1.241	1.174	0.242	61.930	๐
		Private	2.923	1.186	-0.468	0.642	58.462	๐
2.	All members of the board have skills in financial, technical, marketing and professional specialties.	Public	3.364	1.116	4.925	0.000	67.281	๒
		Private	3.404	0.975	2.986	0.004	68.077	๓
3.	The structure of the Board of Directors shall take into account the separation between the function of the Presidency of the Council and the Executive Directorate and not to collect them in one person.	Public	3.320	1.262	3.830	0.000	66.404	๔
		Private	3.423	1.289	2.367	0.022	68.462	๒
4.	The responsibilities of the board are clear.	Public	3.351	1.168	4.534	0.000	67.018	๓
		Private	3.385	1.087	2.551	0.014	67.692	๔
5.	The board of directors of the university is formed democratically.	Public	3.399	1.232	4.891	0.000	67.982	๑
		Private	3.577	1.073	3.878	0.000	71.538	๑
Fields as a whole		Public	3.306	0.988	4.677	0.000	66.123	
		Private	3.342	0.786	3.139	0.003	66.846	
The principle of academic freedom								
1.	Teaching their students in the manner and courses they deem appropriate.	Public	3.636	1.030	9.324	0.000	72.719	๑
		Private	3.827	0.985	6.056	0.000	76.538	๑
2.	Intellectual meetings between faculty members at the university.	Public	3.303	0.994	4.599	0.000	66.053	๔
		Private	3.519	0.960	3.901	0.000	70.385	๔
3.	Participation with local community sectors.	Public	3.588	0.858	10.339	0.000	71.754	๒
		Private	3.558	0.916	4.389	0.000	71.154	๓
4.	Motivation to organize cultural seminars for community members on different occasions.	Public	3.504	0.893	8.529	0.000	70.088	๓
		Private	3.577	1.091	3.814	0.000	71.538	๒
5.	The University imposes restrictions on faculty members because of their views.	Public	3.053	1.133	0.701	0.484	61.053	๐
		Private	2.769	1.165	-1.428	0.159	55.385	๐
Fields as a whole		Public	3.417	0.629	10.007	0.000	68.333	
		Private	3.450	0.539	6.026	0.000	69.000	
Principles of Governance		Public	3.363	0.578	9.495	0.000	67.269	
		Private	3.349	0.527	4.768	0.000	66.974	

The previous table shows the following:

- The availability of the principles of governance in public universities came at a relative weight (67.269), which is (intermediate). In private universities, the relative weight was 66.974. Public universities are more interested in governance than private universities, where they have a higher interest in governance and better education and management. However, in general, universities

suffer from weak governance due to the multiplicity of regulatory bodies, the spread of patronage, temperament and the speed of change. Universities need autonomy to achieve excellence. This finding is consistent with Al-Arini (2014) and Mahrous (2016).

- The availability of laws and regulations in public universities came at a relative weight of 72.421, which is a large degree. Private universities had a

relative weight of 73.077, which is a large degree. This is due to the fact that laws and regulations are the only guarantee for employees' rights and reflect the values of justice and integrity adopted by the university in their transactions. Therefore, they must be reviewed periodically to suit the changes in the environment.

- The availability of transparency and disclosure in public universities came at a relative weight of (63.895), which is (intermediate). In private universities, the relative weight was 60.846, which is (intermediate). This is because transparency has positive effects both in public and private universities because it helps to promote loyalty and belonging to employees and increase their productivity, in addition to strengthening the values of cooperation, reducing ambiguity and obscurity, eliminating corruption, facilitating performance evaluation and reducing time and costs.
- The availability of accounting and accountability in public universities came at a relative weight of (67.421), which is (intermediate), and in private universities it was relatively high (69.231), which is (large). This is because accountability plays a major role in promoting transparency and business ethics, as well as enhancing trust among individuals within the university with the outside community.
- The availability of the rights of all the beneficiaries in the public universities came at a relative weight of (65.421), which is (intermediate). In private universities, the relative weight was 62.846. This means that the University is aware of the rights of all interested parties, which are included in the

regulations and laws, and also supports and encourages joint cooperation between them and those parties.

- The availability of the responsibilities of the board of directors in the public universities came at a relative weight (66.123), which is (intermediate). In private universities, the relative weight was 66.846, which is (intermediate). One of the most important requirements for improving the performance of universities is the existence of a management capable of carrying out its responsibilities with expertise, qualifications and skills that enable it to achieve excellence in university education.
- The availability of academic freedom in public universities came at a relative weight of 68.333, which is a large degree. In private universities, the relative weight was 69.000 which is a large degree. Academic freedom is one of the most important solutions that can be invested to achieve quality in university life and activate participation by stakeholders and beneficiaries of the educational service.

10.2 Results of the second question:

The question is: What is the extent to which universities support partnership (partnership vision, mission and objectives, partnership organization and management, implementation of partnership) with community organizations from the point of view of university staff?

This question was answered using the "T" test for one sample, as shown in the following tables:

Table 6: Analysis of the partnership fields

No.	Item	Universities	SMA	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	"Sig." value	Relative weight	Ranking
The fields of vision, mission and goals								
1.	The University's vision includes its vital relationship with community institutions.	Public	3.996	0.712	21.122	0.000	79.912	٢
		Private	3.942	0.802	8.470	0.000	78.846	٢
2.	The University's mission supports active interaction with community institutions.	Public	4.088	0.671	24.472	0.000	81.754	١
		Private	4.096	0.846	9.341	0.000	81.923	١
3.	The University sets clear and specific objectives related to the needs of the surrounding community institutions.	Public	3.873	0.822	16.037	0.000	77.456	٣
		Private	3.923	0.788	8.444	0.000	78.462	٣
4.	The University will involve the parties involved in the development of the strategic objectives of the Partnership.	Public	3.732	0.917	12.067	0.000	74.649	٤
		Private	3.635	0.929	4.924	0.000	72.692	٤

No.	Item	Universities	SMA	Standard Deviation	"T" Value	"Sig." value	Relative weight	Ranking
5.	The University is keen to develop the objectives of the partnership to ensure the strengthening of the link between the University and the surrounding institutions.	Public	3.654	0.854	11.552	0.000	73.070	๐
		Private	3.596	0.799	5.384	0.000	71.923	๐
Fields as a whole		Public	3.868	0.635	20.664	0.000	77.368	
		Private	3.838	0.687	8.799	0.000	76.769	
Fields of partnership organization and management								
1.	The University administration determines the actual needs of the beneficiaries of its outputs.	Public	3.570	0.855	10.072	0.000	71.404	๐
		Private	3.481	0.828	4.186	0.000	69.615	๐
2.	The Department is keen to raise awareness of the culture of partnership between the University and community institutions through holding seminars and conferences.	Public	3.886	0.706	18.958	0.000	77.719	๒
		Private	3.673	0.785	6.182	0.000	73.462	๒
3.	The department publishes successful experiences of partnership between the university and community institutions.	Public	3.754	0.728	15.651	0.000	75.088	๓
		Private	3.577	0.801	5.196	0.000	71.538	๓
4.	The University administration holds agreements for various projects between the university and the local community.	Public	3.969	0.618	23.671	0.000	79.386	๑
		Private	4.038	0.593	12.632	0.000	80.769	๑
5.	The University is interested in measuring the satisfaction of the beneficiaries of the graduates when developing their educational programs.	Public	3.649	0.855	11.464	0.000	72.982	๔
		Private	3.500	0.980	3.678	0.001	70.000	๔
Fields as a whole		Public	3.766	0.547	21.150	0.000	75.316	
		Private	3.654	0.571	8.252	0.000	73.077	
Fields of partnership implementation								
1.	The university coordinates with community institutions to determine the criteria for selecting its students to suit the changes in the labor market.	Public	3.404	1.060	5.750	0.000	68.070	๐
		Private	3.788	1.091	5.213	0.000	75.769	๒
2.	The University sets its programs and decisions in line with the needs of the labor market.	Public	3.798	0.793	15.201	0.000	75.965	๒
		Private	3.769	0.921	6.025	0.000	75.385	๓
3.	University students receive their practical training while studying in the surrounding community-related institutions.	Public	4.066	0.763	21.103	0.000	81.316	๑
		Private	4.154	0.697	11.939	0.000	83.077	๑
4.	The University has active mechanisms for applying its research to community institutions.	Public	3.478	0.873	8.272	0.000	69.561	๓
		Private	3.365	0.991	2.660	0.010	67.308	๔
5.	The University embraces start-up partnership projects to provide direct support and assistance in planning workflows.	Public	3.478	0.959	7.525	0.000	69.561	๓
		Private	3.365	1.010	2.608	0.012	67.308	๔
Fields as a whole		Public	3.645	0.657	14.824	0.000	72.895	
		Private	3.688	0.710	6.992	0.000	73.769	
Partnership		Public	3.760	0.518	22.125	0.000	75.193	
		Private	3.727	0.572	9.169	0.000	74.538	

The above table shows that:

- The public universities' support for partnership with local community organizations was relatively high (75.193), with a large degree. Private universities had a relative weight of (74.538), which is (large). The researchers believe that partnership with the private sector should receive adequate attention and cover all areas such as: scientific research, education and continuing training, counseling, knowledge and cultural exchanges, academic exchanges, etc. This result is consistent with the study of Tetevová (2010), Khater (2015), Abdo (2015), Hristova and Klisarovska (2013) and Okwelle and Wordu (2014).
- The support of public universities for the vision, mission, and objectives of the partnership came at a relative weight of 77.368, which is a large degree. In private universities, it came with a relative weight of 76.769, which is a large degree. The foundation of the partnership is to build the community culture to establish partnership between institutions and to adopt it within the strategic plan of the institution. This requires providing information about the partnership parties and considering the partnership as a vital direction of the strategic directions of the organization.
- Public universities supported the organization and management of the partnership with a relative weight of (75.316), a degree (large), and in private universities came with a relative weight (73.077), a degree (large). This phase requires the actual start of the partnership activities, which include identifying the parties that will facilitate the process

of communication with the local community, and holding permanent meetings to study the problems and work to solve them in order to activate the partnership and reach to the actual implementation, as we find that many agreements and partnerships are held only on The paper does not extend beyond that scope and may not be known to the staff.

- Public universities supported the implementation of the partnership with a relative weight of (72.895), which is (a large degree), and in the private universities came a relative weight (73.769), a degree (large). This stage is one of the most important stages that require constant attention and evaluation of partnership activities and documentation of all phases to benefit from them, with the need to focus on the dissemination of successful experiences.

10.3 Results of the third question:

The question is: To what extent did the principles of governance in universities contribute to strengthening partnership with community organizations from the point of view of university workers? To answer this question, the following hypothesis was formulated:

There is no statistically significant relationship between the application of governance principles and the strengthening of partnerships with community organizations from the point of view of university staff.

This hypothesis has been validated by finding correlation coefficients, as shown in the following table:

Table 7: The relationship between the principles of governance and partnership

No.	The Hub	Public Universities			Private Universities		
		Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance
1.	Vision of the partnership and its mission and objectives	0.728	Sig at 0.01	0.760	Sig at 0.01
2.	Organization and management of partnership	0.649	Sig at 0.01	0.637	Sig at 0.01
3.	Implementation of the partnership	0.841	Sig at 0.01	0.550	Sig at 0.01
Partnership		0.717	Sig at 0.01	0.743	Sig at 0.01

The correlation between the principles of governance and partnership is statistically significant, indicating that there is a statistically significant correlation between the application of the principles of governance in universities and the strengthening of partnership with local community organizations from the point of view of university workers. This finding is consistent with Abdul Hakim (2010) and Abdul Fattah (2013), Harkavy et al. (2014).

The following sub-assumptions are derived from the former President's assumption:

1. **There is no statistically significant relationship between applying the principle of laws and regulations in universities and strengthening partnership with local community organizations from the point of view of university workers.**

Table 8: Relationship between the principle of laws and regulations and partnership

No.	The Hub	Public Universities	Private Universities
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		Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance
1.	Vision of the partnership and its mission and objectives	0.864	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.641	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
2.	Organization and management of partnership	0.507	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.716	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
3.	Implementation of the partnership	0.698	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.597	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
	Partnership	0.882	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.830	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01

The above table shows that correlation coefficients between the principle of laws and regulations and the partnership is statistically significant. This indicates a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between applying the principle of laws and regulations in universities and strengthening partnership with community organizations from the point of view of workers Universities.

2. **There is no statistically significant relationship between the application of the principle of transparency and disclosure in universities and the promotion of partnership with local community organizations from the point of view of university staff.**

Table 9: The relationship between the principle of transparency and disclosure and partnership

No.	The Hub	Public Universities			Private Universities		
		Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance
1.	Vision of the partnership and its mission and objectives	0.794	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.817	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
2.	Organization and management of partnership	0.900	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.654	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
3.	Implementation of the partnership	0.808	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.861	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
	Partnership	0.725	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.743	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01

The correlation between the principle of transparency and disclosure and the partnership is statistically significant. This indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the application of the principle of transparency and disclosure in the universities and strengthening the partnership with local community organizations from the point of view of workers Universities.

3. **There is no statistically significant relationship between the application of accounting and accountability in universities and the promotion of partnership with local community organizations from the point of view of university staff.**

Table 10: The relationship between the principle of accountability and accountability and partnership

No.	The Hub	Public Universities			Private Universities		
		Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance
1.	Vision of the partnership and its mission and objectives	0.776	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.875	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
2.	Organization and management of partnership	0.638	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.651	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
3.	Implementation of the partnership	0.729	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.912	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01
	Partnership	0.914	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01	0.908	∗∗∗∗	Sig at 0.01

The correlation between accountability and partnership is statistically significant. This indicates a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the

application of accountability and accountability in universities and the strengthening of partnership with local

community organizations from the point of view of workers Universities.

4. There is no statistically significant relationship between the application of the principle of interest in the rights of all the beneficiaries in the universities

and the promotion of partnership with community organizations from the point of view of university workers.

Table 11: Relationship between the principle of concern for the rights of all the beneficiaries and partnership

No.	The Hub	Public Universities			Private Universities		
		Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance
1.	Vision of the partnership and its mission and objectives	0.746	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.729	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01
2.	Organization and management of partnership	0.654	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.872	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01
3.	Implementation of the partnership	0.784	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.781	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01
	Partnership	0.851	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.839	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01

The above table shows that correlation coefficients between the principle of interest in the rights of all the beneficiaries and the partnership is statistically significant, indicating that there is a statistically significant relationship at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the application of the principle of interest in the rights of all the beneficiaries in the universities, From the point of view of university workers.

5. There is no statistically significant relationship between the application of the principle of determining the responsibilities of the board of directors in universities and strengthening the partnership with local community organizations from the point of view of university workers.

Table 12: Relationship between the principle of determining the responsibilities of the Board of Directors and partnership

No.	The Hub	Public Universities			Private Universities		
		Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance
1.	Vision of the partnership and its mission and objectives	0.761	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.838	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01
2.	Organization and management of partnership	0.527	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.757	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01
3.	Implementation of the partnership	0.721	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.773	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01
	Partnership	0.929	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.849	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01

The correlation between the principle of determining the responsibilities of the board of directors and the partnership is statistically significant. This indicates a statistically significant relationship at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the application of the principle of determining the responsibilities of the board of directors in the universities and strengthening the

partnership with the local community organizations from the point of view of university employees.

6. There is no statistically significant relationship between the application of the principle of academic freedom in universities and the promotion of partnership with community organizations from the point of view of university workers.

Table 13: Relationship between the principle of academic freedom and partnership

No.	The Hub	Public Universities			Private Universities		
		Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance	Coefficient of correlation	“Sig.” value	Level of significance
1.	Vision of the partnership and its mission and objectives	0.668	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.665	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01
2.	Organization and	0.752	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01	0.768	·.·.·.	Sig at 0.01

	management of partnership						
3.	Implementation of the partnership	0.773	••••	Sig at 0.01	0.917	••••	Sig at 0.01
	Partnership	0.869	••••	Sig at 0.01	0.846	••••	Sig at 0.01

The above table shows that correlation coefficients between the principle of academic freedom and partnership are statistically significant. This indicates a statistically significant relationship between the application of the principle of academic freedom in universities and the strengthening of partnership with community organizations from the point of view of workers Universities.

10.4 Results of the fourth question:

Question: Do respondents differ on the contribution of governance to the promotion of partnership in Palestinian

Table 14: Differences for the variable of the scientific qualification

Scale	Qualification	The Number	SMA	Standard Deviation	"F" value	"Sig." value	Level of significance
Governance	Ph.D.	76	3.334	0.438	1.859	0.137	Not Sig.
	M.A.	80	3.450	0.590			
	BA	113	3.355	0.597			
	Diploma	30	3.173	0.599			
Partnership	Ph.D.	76	3.698	0.471	2.222	0.086	Not Sig.
	M.A.	80	3.790	0.600			
	BA	113	3.809	0.447			
	Diploma	30	3.560	0.654			

* The value of the "F" table at the degree of freedom (3, 295) and at the level of significance (0.05) = (3.070)

The above table shows that the value of the calculated "F" is less than the "F" value in the government and partnership scale. This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between respondents' opinions on university governance and partnership according to the scientific qualification from the point of view of university workers. This result is different from Al-Arini (2014).

universities according to the number of years of service, university, and university level? To answer this question, the following assumptions were formulated:

1. **There were no statistically significant differences between respondents' views on university governance and the promotion of partnership with local community organizations according to the academic qualification from the point of view of university staff.**

This hypothesis has been validated by the One-Way ANOVA test, as shown in the following table:

2. **There were no statistically significant differences between respondents' views on university governance and strengthening partnership with local community organizations according to the number of years of service from the point of view of university staff.**

This hypothesis has been validated by the One-Way ANOVA test, as shown in the following table:

Table 15: Variance for the variable number of years of service

Scale	Number of years of service	The Number	SMA	Standard Deviation	"F" value	"Sig." value	Level of significance
Governance	Less than 5 years	70	3.186	0.598	4.943	0.002	Sig.
	From 5 - less than 10 years	93	3.304	0.575			
	From 10 - under 15 years	87	3.501	0.500			
	15 years and over	49	3.445	0.519			
Partnership	Less than 5 years	70	3.742	0.605	0.646	0.586	Not Sig.
	From 5 - less than 10 years	93	3.697	0.483			
	From 10 - under 15 years	87	3.779	0.504			

	15 years and over	49	3.814	0.514			
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* The value of the "F" table at the degree of freedom (3. 295) and at the level of significance (0.05) = (3.070)

The above table shows that the value of the calculated "F" is greater than the "F" value in the government scale. This indicates statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between respondents' opinions on university governance according to the number of years of service Look at university workers, and for those who have years of service (from 10 - under 15 years). And the absence of statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between respondents' opinions on strengthening partnership with local community organizations according to the number

of years of service from the point of view of university employees. This finding is consistent with Al-Arini (2014).

3. There were no statistically significant differences between respondents' views on university governance and the promotion of partnership with local community organizations according to the university from the point of view of university staff.

This hypothesis has been validated by the One-Way ANOVA test, as shown in the following table:

Table 16: Differences for University Variable

Scale	University	The Number	SMA	Standard Deviation	"F" value	"Sig." value	Level of significance
Governance	Islamic University	145	3.389	0.591	0.516	0.671	Not Sig.
	Palestine University	48	3.362	0.538			
	Al Azhar university	97	3.300	0.548			
	University of Gaza	9	3.411	0.328			
Partnership	Islamic University	145	3.838	0.430	4.309	0.005	Not Sig.
	Palestine University	48	3.704	0.589			
	Al Azhar university	97	3.620	0.606			
	University of Gaza	9	4.000	0.133			

* The value of the "F" table at the degree of freedom (3. 295) and at the level of significance (0.05) = (3.070)

The above table shows that the value of the calculated "F" is less than the "F" value in the government scale. This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the opinions of the respondents on university governance, University workers. And that the value of the calculated "F" is greater than the value of the "F" in the scale of the partnership, indicating that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between respondents' opinions on

strengthening the partnership with community organizations, Universities, and for the University of Gaza.

10.5 Results of the fifth question:

The question is as follows: What are the constraints to the application of university partnerships with community organizations from the point of view of university workers?

This question was answered using the "T" test for one sample, as shown in the following table:

Table 17: Analysis of the issues of the axis of constraints that limit the application of the partnership

No.	Item	Universities	SMA	Standard Deviation	"T" Values	"Sig." value	Relative weight	Ranking
1.	The scarcity of funding for the partnership.	Public	3.693	0.930	11.246	0.000	73.860	٢
		Private	3.635	0.841	5.442	0.000	72.692	٢
2.	Limited powers granted to universities.	Public	3.711	0.771	13.918	0.000	74.211	١
		Private	3.654	0.814	5.794	0.000	73.077	١
3.	Low prioritization and needs of society.	Public	3.404	0.753	8.086	0.000	68.070	٨
		Private	3.462	0.917	3.628	0.001	69.231	٣
4.	The priorities of partnership projects are in line with the priorities of the University.	Public	3.526	0.893	8.904	0.000	70.526	٤
		Private	3.365	0.991	2.660	0.010	67.308	٤
5.	Weak confidence of community institutions in the potential contribution of the university to	Public	3.421	1.049	6.063	0.000	68.421	٧
		Private	3.135	0.971	1.000	0.322	62.692	٧

	solve its problems and improve its performance.							
6.	The concentration of universities on theoretical aspects is more than applied aspects.	Public	3.325	0.975	5.024	0.000	66.491	9
		Private	2.808	1.121	-1.237	0.222	56.154	10
7.	Weak communication between the university and community institutions.	Public	2.969	1.196	-0.388	0.699	59.386	10
		Private	2.962	1.188	-0.234	0.816	59.231	9
8.	Weak knowledge of the institutions of the community to what can be provided by the universities.	Public	3.496	0.908	8.245	0.000	69.912	0
		Private	3.288	1.035	2.009	0.050	65.769	6
9.	Lack of laws governing the partnership processes between universities and community institutions.	Public	3.478	0.968	7.454	0.000	69.561	6
		Private	3.096	1.241	0.559	0.579	61.923	8
10.	The University's interest in teaching function is more than scientific research and community service.	Public	3.614	0.881	10.529	0.000	72.281	3
		Private	3.346	1.008	2.478	0.017	66.923	0
Fields as a whole		Public	3.464	0.507	13.795	0.000	69.272	
		Private	3.275	0.625	3.175	0.003	65.500	

The above table shows that the obstacles to the implementation of the public universities' partnership with local community organizations were relatively high (69.272), with a large degree. In the private universities they came in relative weight (65.500), which is (medium). This confirms the existence of constraints to the implementation of partnerships from the perspective of faculty members. It is also clear from the above table that the main obstacles to the implementation of partnerships are (the limited powers granted to universities), and they came in relative weight (74.211), with a (large) degree, and in private universities the same paragraph, has come by relative weight (73.077), which is (large). This makes sense for most central universities to take decisions, which impede the implementation of the partnership. The lowest level of communication between the university and the community institutions was the relative weight of 59.386 in the intermediate grades and in the private universities (6), with a relative weight (56.154), which is (medium). The researchers believe that this is due to the openness of universities to the community and the availability of means of communication, in addition to the focus of universities on the practical side and support. This finding is consistent with the study (AL-Hariri, 2010).

11. CONCLUSIONS

- The results of the study indicated that the level of availability of the principles of governance in the public and private universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of workers was high. The relative weight in the public universities was 67.3%, while the private universities were the relative weight (67%). The order of principles is as follows: (laws and regulations, academic freedom, accounting and accountability, board

responsibilities, the rights of all stakeholders, transparency and disclosure).

- The results showed that the level of partnership in public and private universities from the point of view of workers was high. The relative weight in the public universities was 75.2%, while the private universities were the relative weight (74.5%).
- The results of the study showed that there is a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between governance in all its dimensions and enhancing the partnership between universities and civil society organizations from the point of view of employees in public and private universities.
- The results of the study showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the averages of the employees' degrees on university governance and partnership for the variable of the scientific qualification.
- The results of the study showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the averages of the employees' degrees of university governance in relation to the variable number of years of service and the number of years of service (less than 15 years). And the absence of differences about the partnership due to the number of years of service.
- The results of the study showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the averages of the employees' grades on university governance according to the university. The results of the study showed that there are differences about partnership for the university variable and for private universities (Gaza University).

- The partnership between universities and the community hampered a number of obstacles, with a relative weight of 69.272 in public universities, and private universities with a relative weight of 65.500. Most notably the limited powers granted to universities and the poor funding for the partnership.

12. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Working on the interest and benefit from the principles of governance available in the public and private universities in the Gaza Strip through the preparation of a document for university governance, which includes the identification of the tasks, processes and responsibilities assigned to each member, and specifying the criteria for the selection of each member.
- Emphasis on the foundations and criteria based on specialization, competence, expertise, skill and integrity, not on the basis of moderation and favoritism for the fair selection of the best candidates for employment within institutions of higher education leaders and employees.
- The need to increase the level of partnership between public and private universities on the one hand and community organizations on the other, as well as the need to follow up the Ministry of Education to the extent of commitment of universities in Palestine to the principles and rules of governance. And to oblige all institutions to disclose and transparency standards and to present the outcomes of their work to the beneficiaries of these services.
- To promote the dissemination of a culture of governance among all parties concerned with the University through seminars and courses, issuing bulletins and instructions regulating the rules and rules of proper application, mechanisms of implementation and follow-up, and disclosure of irregularities, weaknesses and shortcomings.
- Supporting the communication between the productive institutions of the community and the university which contributes towards the establishment of a department to develop the university's resources and properties. And interest in providing opportunities for researchers to invest applied research and move scientific efforts from the theoretical framework to the field of work.
- The creation of a special unit for partnership and community development that works to support the positive relationship between the university and the community institutions.
- The need to delegate the senior management of universities to other departments to open channels of communication with other universities and civil society institutions. And attention to human resources and training and familiarize them with the rules and principles of governance in addition to providing them

with all the latest developments and scientific information in this area.

- Optimize the use of all human and material resources, which enable the implementation and compliance of the rules of governance in higher education institutions.
- To eliminate all obstacles that limit the partnership between universities and community organizations, the most important of which are the limited powers granted to universities and the weak funding allocated to partnerships. The Ministry of Education and Higher Education can contribute to supporting partnership projects and the need to link production centers with community needs. During the development of a clear plan and the philosophy and goals and criteria of partnership with the participation of all parties.

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